

Activity Map of EU ALTAI Trustworthy AI Guidelines with AI Management System Standards

Introduction

Organisations must currently navigate a large number of competing and changing guidelines, policies and soon regulations and standards in regard to Trustworthy AI. A lack of mapping between these numerous and diverse guidelines, standards, regulations, and organisational policies makes meeting the requirements and obligations arising from them a challenging task. Trustworthiness can be manifested through characteristics such as privacy, fairness, security, safety, transparency, and accountability¹. These days, the goal of trustworthy AI has become of utmost importance for organisations developing and using AI. Parallel efforts are undertaken by international organisations, national authorities, and the private sector to light the way of organisations in fulfilling trustworthiness requirements. A major step in using these guidelines is to translate high-level, broad, and sometime vague statements of principles into implementable and, potentially, certifiable governance, management and technical operations activities. Taking this essential step towards trustworthy AI realisation is hindered by a lack of proven methods to translate principles into practice^{2 3}.

Another issue that arises after identifying activities is how to integrate these new management activities with the existing ones or more specifically fit them into the organisation's overall management system and thereby resolve potential management system incompatibilities arising from the adoption of AI technology. In general, a management system is a set of interrelated or interacting elements of an organisation to establish policies and objectives, along with processes to achieve those objective. Thus, an AI management

¹ ISO/IEC TR 24028:2020 Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Overview of trustworthiness in artificial intelligence, <https://www.iso.org/standard/77608.html>.

² Mittelstadt, B.: Principles alone cannot guarantee ethical AI. *Nat. Mach. Intell.* 1, 501–507 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42256-019-0114-4>.

³ Schiff, D., Rakova, B., Ayesha, A., Fanti, A., Lennon, M.: Principles to Practices for Responsible AI: Closing the Gap. *ArXiv200604707 Cs.* (2020)

system (AIMS) consists of guidelines, policies, processes and activities to achieve AI objectives including trustworthiness, and is currently being developed by ISO/IEC JTC1/SC42.

AIMS standards and trustworthy AI guidelines developed separately and in isolation risk a highly fragmented landscape that can lead to regulatory and market confusion. Therefore, there is a need to assess the inconsistencies, gaps, and areas of overlap. Mapping EU trustworthy AI guidelines into prospective AI management system standards may therefore provide useful insights for both standardisation bodies and regulators.

For this initial mapping, we focus on the trustworthy AI framework developed by the European Commission's High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (AI-HLEG)⁴, Future EU regulations for AI are expected to be aligned to the AI-HLEG recommendations so they provide a good initial basis for mapping AIMS to EU AI principles. Further, the AI-HLEG published an assessment list for trustworthy AI (ALTAI)⁵ which serves as a complement to the framework and includes a detailed checklist to enable organisations to self-assess their alignment with AI-HLEG AI principles. The ALTAI questions therefore provide a basis for identifying organisational management activities for meeting the trustworthiness requirements in the lifecycle and application of AI systems. In this initial assessment we conduct a mapping organisational activities derived from the ALTAI checklist and those anticipated for a future AI MSS.

Approach to activity modelling of ALTAI

To put it simply, ALTAI is a document containing a list of questions and by answering them, an organisation can find its place on the road to

⁴ High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence: Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI, <https://ec.europa.eu/futurium/en/ai-alliance-consultation/guidelines>, (2019).

⁵ High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence: The Assessment List for Trustworthy AI (ALTAI) for self assessment, (2020) <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence-altai-self-assessment>

trustworthy AI. It provides a short descriptions, key terms and questions grouped by the trustworthy AI requirement they aim to assess.

ALTAI document consists of 8 sections where one is devoted to fundamental rights and the rest represent trustworthy AI requirements. Each section encompasses two or more subsections; for instance, Traceability (Trc), Explainability (Exp), and Communication (Com) are part of the Transparency (Trs) section. Under each subsection, questions concerning that specific issue are presented.

ALTAI involves information on what activities are needed to be planned and executed regarding trustworthy AI. Therefore, it is not only useful as a trustworthy AI compliance checking tool but also is a basis for identifying the activities needed for implementing the trustworthy requirements.

To formulate a mapping between ALTAI and the AIMS standard, the activities implied by the questions within both must be made explicit. For the purpose of the comparison, we only extract management activities though there are technical and operational activities that can be pulled out of the questions. Table 1 presents examples of ALTAI activities

Table 1. Examples of management activities extracted from ALTAI.

ID	ALTAI Question	ALTAI Management Activity
FRQ3	Does the AI system protect personal data relating to individuals in line with GDPR?	Assess whether the AI system protects personal data relating to individuals in line with GDPR.
HAAQ1.2	Are end-users or other subjects adequately made aware that a decision, content, advice or outcome is the result of an algorithmic decision?	Inform end-users or other subjects that a decision, content, advice or outcome is the result of an algorithmic decision.

RFPRQ4	Did you put in place a proper procedure for handling the cases where the AI system yields results with a low confidence score?	Establish a procedure for handling the cases where the AI system yields results with a low confidence score.
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Approach to activity modelling of AIMS

As of April 2021, no AIMS standard is published, however an AIMS standard is being developed by ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42 Artificial intelligence committee⁶. This standard, like any other management system standard, shall follow the High-Level Structure (HLS) defined in ISO/IEC Directives, Part 1⁷. This HLS alongside the identical subclause titles, identical text and common terms and core definitions provides a common core for all management system standards developed by ISO. In advance of SC42 project reaching consensus on how it elaborate the LHL for AI and aligns this with other SC42 standards under development, this analysis restricts its model of AIMS activities to those MSS activities identified in the HL, essentially replace the blank IT system and management system reference with AI system and AI Management System (AIMS).

Based on the HLS, Lewis et al.⁸ identify a set of 17 AIMS activities where each is given an identifier, a label, and a 'see also' attribute which is a link to the relevant HLS clause (Table 2). Also, the entities generated and used by each activity are represented in a similar manner.

Table 2. AIMS activities.

⁶ ISO/IEC AWI 42001 Information Technology — Artificial intelligence — Management system, <https://www.iso.org/standard/81230.html>

⁷ ISO/IEC Directives, Part 1 — Consolidated ISO Supplement — Procedures specific to ISO, (2020) <https://www.iso.org/sites/directives/current/consolidated/index.xhtml>

⁸ Lewis, D., Filip, D., Pandit, H.J.: An Ontology for Standardising Trustworthy AI, (2021). <http://www.tara.tcd.ie/handle/2262/96114>

#	AIMS activity ID	AIMS Activity (label)	HLS clause (see also)
1	UOC	Understanding organisation and its context	4.1
2	USE	Understanding stakeholder needs and expectation	4.2
3	DS	Determine AIMS scope	4.3
4	EP	Establish AIMS policy	5.2
5	ARRA	Assign roles, responsibilities and authorities	5.3
6	ARO	Address risks and opportunities	6.1
7	EPAO	Establish and plan to achieve AI objectives	6.2
8	DAR	Determine and allocate resources for AIMS	7.1
9	DEC	Determine and ensure competence of people affecting AI performance	7.2
10	PA	Promote awareness	7.3
11	DC	Determine AIMS communication	7.4
12	PCP	Plan and control AI processes	8.1
13	MMAE	Monitor, measure, analyse and evaluate AI	9.1
14	IA	Internal (AIMS) audit	9.2
15	UMR	Undertake management review	9.3
16	DNCA	Detect non-conformance and take corrective action	10.1
17	CI	AIMS Continual improvement	10.2

ALTAI and AIMS activity mapping

To bridge these two isolated sets of activities, we use the partOf relationship. The main objective of this alignment is to discover to what extent ALTAI addresses AIMS activities. This objective is translated into the following competency questions:

- Is there any ALTAI activity that cannot be mapped into AIMS activities?
- What AIMS activities are not represented in ALTAI?
- Which ALTAI activities are part of a specific AIMS activity, e.g. addressing risk and opportunities (ARO)?
- Does ALTAI suggest any activity for AIMS improvement?

- What AIMS activities are involved in achieving a particular trustworthy AI requirement, e.g. privacy and data governance?

ALTAI-AIMS Mapping Groups

In the activity mapping process, a number of commonly occurring structures are identified. For instance, there are multiple ALTAI activities that refer to achieving AI objectives such as accuracy, accessibility, usability, reliability, explainability, privacy, and fairness. Such ALTAI activities have a partOf relationship with ‘establish and plan to achieve AI objectives’ activity (EPAO in Table 2). We categorise these structures into mapping groups. The full list of mapping groups is listed in Table 3.

The mapping is carried out by analysing each ALTAI activity to find the part of relation based on the description of the AIMS activities presented in the HLS. For example, in establishing processes for AI risk mitigation, the organisation has to determine AI risks treatments as well as implement and control processes needed for risk mitigation. Hence, ALTAI activities that are devoted to establishing processes (or procedures, mechanisms, measures) to mitigate, rectify, or avoid AI risks are part of both ‘addressing risks and opportunities’ (ARO in Table 2) and ‘plan and control processes’ (PCP in Table 2). As demonstrated in the table, the mapping is many-to-many and an ALTAI activity could be mapped into up to three AIMS activities.

Table 3. ALTAI-AIMS activity mapping groups.

ID	ALTAI Activity Structure	partOf (AIMS activity)
MG1	Assess the impact of the AI system	ARO
MG2	Assess the system vulnerabilities or threats	ARO
MG3	Assess whether the AI system respects a specific right	ARO
MG4	Establish processes to test or monitor AI impacts or risks	PCP & ARO & MMAE

MG5	Establish processes to measure and assess AI risks	PCP & ARO
MG6	Establish processes to mitigate, rectify, or avoid AI risks	PCP & ARO
MG7	Establish processes to achieve an AI objective	PCP & EPAO
MG8	Assess whether an AI objective is achieved	EPAO & MMAE
MG9	Establish processes to test and monitor AI objectives	PCP & EPAO & MMAE
MG10	Establish processes to measure and assess AI objectives	PCP & EPAO & MMAE
MG11	Provide information about a design decision (a feature of the system or a fact about it)	UOC
MG12	Determine whether the systems is certified for or compliant with a specific standard or guideline/ Align the system with that standard	PCP & UOC
MG13	Designate a role	ARRA
MG14	Establish a broad (e.g. ethics review board)	ARRA
MG15	Provide training for employees to ensure their competence/ Ensure competence of workers	DEC
MG16	Communicate (consult) with or inform users or third parties	DC
MG17	Inform staff and employees about the AI policy (e.g. legal framework applicable to the AI system) or AI objectives	PA

Insights from Mapping

The mapping exercise reveals that ALTAI is centred around the trustworthy AI issues and principles rather than how to manage trustworthy AI processes and policies within an organisation. In

comparison, AIMS does not specifically refer to any trustworthy principle, however, it provides a foundation for implementing these principles in an organisation. The two are therefore complementary regarding effective implementation and assessment of trustworthy AI, with the alignment providing a way to achieve trustworthiness through AIMS activities.

Table 4 presents the number of ALTAI activities that are mapped into each AIMS activity. It should be noted that the total number indicates the number of times an AIMS activity is individually mapped to ALTAI activities as the mapping between the two is many-to-many. For brevity, the total number of activities within ALTAI is 144, and that within AIMS is 17. Activities within AIMS that do not have a corresponding ALTAI activity are omitted from the table (8 in total).

Table 4. Number of ALTAI activities mapped into each AIMS activity.

AIMS activity ID	AIMS Activity (label)	No. of ALTAI activities
ARO	Address risks and opportunities	73
PCP	Plan and control AI processes	54
EPAO	Establish and plan to achieve AI objectives	44
DC	Determine AIMS communication	22
MMAE	Monitor, measure, analyse and evaluate AI	20
UOC	Understanding organisation and its context	12
DEC	Determine and ensure competence of people affecting AI performance	7
ARRA	Assign roles, responsibilities and authorities	2
PA	Promote awareness	2

The table shows that approximately 50 percent (73 of 144) of ALTAI activities refer to risk management which makes clear the fact that ALTAI adopts a risk-oriented approach towards trustworthy AI. The missing AIMS activities in the table, which are nearly half of total, demonstrates that processes and tasks at a high level of organisational governance and management are not covered in ALTAI. Documents that specify guidelines generally refer to activities and processes across three distinct phases: ex-ante where a plan of activity

must exist; ongoing or during where an activity is currently in the process of being executed; and ex-post where an activity has finished execution or has produced artefacts. For AI guidelines, it is important to model the corresponding semantic representation of activities in a similar manner so as to distinguish when an organisation or system must have a *plan* in place representing some *future activity* versus having carried out that activity i.e. *in the past*. This notion is also applicable and demonstrated in the area of legal and regulatory compliance where an obligation can entail provenance of both a plan as well as executed activities, and therefore requires documentation at both ex-ante and ex-post phase⁹.

Intended for self-assessment purposes, ALTAI predominately refers to the ex-post phase. This means that to provide answers to ALTAI questions we have to look into the results and artefacts of executed activities. Furthermore, separation between ex-ante and ex-post phases of ALTAI activities enables ex-ante planning for trustworthiness and ex-post trustworthy AI (self-) assessment as outlined by AIMS activities. However, for semantic representation of the activities extracted from ALTAI both planning and execution phases should be taken into account. For example, from 'establish processes to assess AI risks' two activities are inferred: plan for AI risk assessment (ex-ante) and AI risk assessment (ex-post). A semantic model of the former should be able to represent plans for risk assessment, intended steps and actions, responsible parties, and entities generated and used during the planning.

Possible Next Steps

The following further analyses are considered:

1. The release of the EC's proposed AI regulation for the EU could be analysed to extract required activities and mapped against

⁹ Pandit, H.J., O'Sullivan, D., Lewis, D.: Test-Driven Approach Towards GDPR Compliance. In: Acosta, M., Cudré-Mauroux, P., Maleshkova, M., Pellegrini, T., Sack, H., and Sure-Vetter, Y. (eds.) *Semantic Systems. The Power of AI and Knowledge Graphs*. pp. 19–33. Springer International Publishing, Cham (2019). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-33220-4_2

the ALTAI This would help identify what aspects of trustworthy AI may and may not be subject to regulation.

2. Activities extracted from the EC's proposed AI regulation could be mapped to the AIMS activities from the HLS template
3. At the end of April 2021, the ISO directive related to MSS was updated with the HLS revised and re-terms as a harmonised MSS structure. In parallel SC42 WG 1 is continuing to work on 42000 AIMS specification. The AIMS activity model should be aligned to these.
4. Activity mapping only provides a partial mapping between ALTAI, the AI Regulation proposal and AIMS, so a direct comparison of concepts, including those proposed in SC42 terminology and concept project 22989 could be undertaken.
5. The mapping between the AI regulation and AIMS could also be mapped in terms of normative language and the requirements detailed therein.

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